

CLOSED EYE DETECTION FOR DRIVERS MONITORING APPLICATION

Carolina Barusso¹, Leonardo Knoeller¹, Marianna Belliero¹, Guilherme de Almeida Rey Dominguez¹, Giovanni Gonçalves Bovolato¹, Arnaldo de Carvalho Junior^{1,2}, Walter Augusto Varella^{1,2}

¹Federal Institute of São Paulo (IFSP), Cubatão – Brazil

²Maxwell Laboratory of Microwaves and Applied Electromagnetism at the Federal Institute of São Paulo (IFSP), Cubatão – Brazil

Abstract- This paper highlights the importance of closed eyes detection for driver's attention monitoring and fatigue detection. Real-time detection of closed eyes allows immediate alerts, preventing accidents due to lack of attention. The Edge Impulse platform is an affordable and efficient solution to achieve this. The Edge Impulse's localized processing capability reduces dependence on network connections, making it a good way for monitoring in real-time. Integration with existing vehicle systems provides fast and effective feedback. This innovative solution increases road safety, reducing accidents and improving driver attention.

Keywords: Edge Impulse; closed eyes detection; driver monitoring; localized processing.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that approximately 1.35 million individuals lose their lives each year because of traffic accidents. Furthermore, between 20 million and 50 million people experience non-lethal accidents, frequently leading to enduring disabilities. In the context of Brazil, the Brazilian Association of Traffic Medicine highlights that fatigue is accountable for 42% of traffic incidents [1].

The increase in the number of vehicles and activities on the roads raises a growing concern regarding the prevention of accidents and the protection of lives [2]. Awareness, supervision, and investment in safe infrastructure are essential to achieve safer transport for everyone. However, driver fatigue and distraction, combined with drowsiness while operating a vehicle, have been recognized as prominent contributors to serious traffic accidents [1], [3]. Faced with this challenge, closed-eye detection has emerged as a promising technology to combat this problem and promote road safety [4]. In this scenario, the adoption of a closed-eye detection system for driver monitoring takes on paramount significance. Under these circumstances, Edge Impulse [5] emerges, a development platform focused on machine learning (ML), specially designed for high-end devices [6].

Edge Impulse offers a complete and affordable solution for creating machine learning models that can be directly deployed to resource-constrained devices [7], such as systems embedded in vehicles. This approach allows real-time detection of closed eyes, providing an immediate alert to the driver and preventing potential accidents resulting from lack of attention [8].

Edge Impulse offers a significant benefit in its ability for local processing, reducing reliance on stable network connections as a key advantage. [7]. This feature is particularly relevant in driver monitoring scenarios, where detection needs to be carried out in real-time, without significant delays caused by network latency.

Implementing closed-eye detection through Edge Impulse brings several benefits to road safety. Early detection of closed eyes allows the driver to be alerted immediately and take action to avoid accidents, especially in situations of fatigue or drowsiness [4].

Furthermore, implementing an Edge Impulse-based driver monitoring system can be easily integrated with existing vehicle systems, such as audio or vibration alerts, providing fast and effective feedback to the driver [9].

In summary, the ability to detect eye closure and monitor it in the traffic environment through Edge Impulse represents an innovative and promising solution to enhance driver and road safety. This solution offers a practical and effective approach, utilizing local processing capacity and ease of integration with embedded devices. By employing this technology, we can strive for a future with fewer traffic accidents and more attentive drivers.

The interest of developing this project is to meet a present need in the safety of driving vehicles, since, as discussed, drowsiness is one of the most worrying causes of accidents.

The help of technology to identify drowsiness symptoms helps to make drivers aware of their drowsy state and issue an alert, so the driver can decide whether to continue driving in that state or not.

This work aims to build Artificial Intelligence capable of detecting closed eyes for application in monitoring drivers. For this project, the use of the Edge Impulse platform was covered from the script, data collection, learning the algorithm, and implementation.

METHODOLOGY

This project uses the Tiny Machine Learning Kit, with the board known as Arduino Nano 33 BLE Sense and the OV7675 camera to capture images. The application has a plug-and-play format, allowing its use in passenger and commercial vehicles manufactured since 2000 when OBD2 (On Board Diagnostics) was standardized. The microcontroller board is powered by pins 4, 5, and 16 of the vehicle's OBD2 output, as shown in Fig. 1. An LM2596 Adjustable Voltage Regulator Module voltage regulator is used to adapt the 3.2 input range at 40V, enabling application in vehicles of different types, such as 12V cars, 24V trucks, and buses.

Fig. 2 presents the block diagram of the proposal for future implementation to plan the use of this Artificial Intelligence developed to act in an embedded manner [10]. Fig. 2 also shows the assembly flow of the project, using OBD2 in conjunction with a voltage

regulator to supply power to the Arduino microcontroller board, and the OV7675 camera, for image capture and alarm. The camera is used in this project to collect information that will be used in real-time to determine, based on the recognition of closed or open eyes, whether the alarm should be triggered or not.

Fig. 1- OBD2 Connector and pins.
 Source: Adapted from [10]

Fig. 2- Block Diagram.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To transfer data to the Edge Impulse platform, it is necessary to assign labels to the unlabeled images within the labeling queue [9]. In this scenario, there are two separate categories that the model will undergo training to distinguish: "Closed Eyes" and "Open Eyes."

Fig. 3- Collected Data.

Consequently, it is imperative to assign two corresponding labels to the images within the labeling queue. This procedure of annotating the data stands as a crucial stage in the object detection model training process. It facilitates the model in acquiring an understanding of the distinct attributes and traits of each category, thereby enabling accurate image categorization and object identification in future scenarios. By meticulously and precisely annotating the images within the labeling queue, you guarantee the model's thorough training and its capacity to perform efficiently. Fig. 3 shows all 174 figures collected for training and 37 for testing already labeled.

By adjusting the model training settings and employing the correct techniques to prevent overfitting, it is possible to optimize the machine learning model's performance and attain a satisfactory level of accuracy suitable for real-world use. By preparing and selecting an appropriate amount of training data for the model, it is achievable to reach a training accuracy of 98.6%, as seen in Figure 4, which is considered a satisfactory outcome.

In Fig. 5, a scatterplot is presented that illustrates the model's ability to distinguish the two categories of data. The greater the distance between categories, the greater the classification accuracy. However, if the data is too close together or if there is overlap without a clear differentiation pattern, accuracy will be drastically reduced, which will compromise model performance.

Fig. 4- Confusion and Accuracy Matrix.

Fig. 5- Dispersion graph.

After the training phase of the machine learning model, an evaluation of its performance on unseen test data is conducted. This involves accessing the Model Test tab and executing the "Sort All" function, allowing us to assess the model's effectiveness in handling the test data and gain valuable insights into its generalization capabilities.

As depicted in Fig. 6, a test accuracy of 97.3% was attained, underscoring the model's outstanding performance. Assessing a machine learning model's performance on unobserved data is crucial for obtaining a realistic assessment of its capabilities.

Relying solely on training data for testing can yield overly optimistic outcomes, given that the model has already been exposed to and learned from this data. By evaluating its performance on unobserved data, a more precise assessment of the model's capacity to generalize and make predictions on novel, unfamiliar inputs can be achieved.

Fig. 6- Real accuracy test.

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the real-time visualization of the model inference, indicating whether the eyes are open (Fig. 7) or closed (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7- Real-time view of opened eye.

Furthermore, the model provided presents a 100% certainty regarding the mentioned inference, as demonstrated by the number adjacent to the text "Open_Eye" and a certainty of 85% and 99% for "Closed_Eye". This number, which conforms to a scale of 0.0 to 1.0, represents the precision or accuracy of the response. Therefore, it can be seen that the inference is highly reliable and accurate.

Fig. 8- Real-time view of closed eye.

CONCLUSION

This article addressed the development of artificial intelligence (AI) to detect driver drowsiness based on the difference between closed eyes and open eyes. Test results showed high AI accuracy in detecting drowsiness, validated by live testing. However, it is essential to remember that AI complements existing safety measures and does not replace the driver's responsibility to remain alert and rested. This technology can reduce the risk of fatigue-related accidents, increasing road safety for vehicle occupants and other users. In the future, it is recommended to expand the database for AI training to consider recognizing open and closed eyes for different ethnicities, lighting conditions in the vehicle cabin, and add features such as sound alerts to wake the driver in case of drowsiness detected.

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